

THE ROLE OF FUNCTIONAL LITERACY IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

Isagalieva Sadafkhon Mukhammadaminovna

Teacher of FerSU

Abstract. *Teaching biology is a field that requires a unique methodology. This article examines the importance, forms and development issues of functional literacy in the process of teaching biological sciences.*

Keywords: *biology, functional literacy, information, method, education.*

INTRODUCTION

Today, the main functional qualities of an individual are the ability to think creatively and find innovative solutions, initiative, the ability to choose a professional path, and the willingness to learn throughout life. Literacy is the level of a person's education, the ability to use the basic methods of cognitive activity through the perception and transmission of information.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Functional literacy is a person's ability to enter into relationships with the external environment and adapt and function in it as quickly as possible. In the processes of learning and education at all times, it was important to link effectively acquired knowledge in a person's future life activities, which made it possible for the younger generation to harmoniously enter society and become its full member. The components of functional literacy are: elements of lexical literacy; human compliance with the norms of social life and safety rules, information and computer literacy.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At the present stage, a competent approach allows us to achieve the results required by society. The process of training graduates at school should be focused on the development of competencies. Competence combines both skills and intellectual abilities in education. A prerequisite for the development of individual competence is the presence of a certain level of functional literacy.

Regulatory documents of the educational process are aimed at preparing students for everyday life, as well as developing their personality with the help of the above-mentioned subject taught. These requirements can be implemented thanks to specially prepared tasks, namely, competency-oriented tasks that help improve the level and quality of students' training, understanding the use of biology knowledge in all types

of human activities, and creating the necessary prerequisites for practical and creative activity.

The competency approach is a set of all general principles for determining the goals of education, selecting and analyzing the content of education, organizing the educational process and assessing the educational results obtained from the work done. The use of competence in education requires making fundamental changes in the organization of the educational process, in its management, in the work of teachers and lecturers, in the ways and methods of assessing the educational results of students in comparison with the educational process based on the concept of mastering knowledge, skills, and abilities. In this case, the main value becomes not the assimilation of the subject of biology as such, the amount of information and knowledge about it, but the development by students of such skills and abilities that would allow them to determine their goals, make the right decisions, and act correctly in typical and non-standard situations. There is no doubt that the position of the teacher and teacher must change fundamentally. They must organize the independent activities of students in such a way that each student can make maximum use and further realize their abilities and interests. Competencies are differentiated by their importance.

1. *Key competencies* – relate to the general content of education.

2. *General subject competencies* - relate to a certain range of educational areas and academic subjects.

3. *Subject competencies* – having a specific description and the possibility of formation within educational subjects and are private in relation to the two previous levels of competence.

In accordance with the categories of resources that are used by a person in the personal and professional spheres (information resources, other people and groups of people, personal qualities and capabilities of the person himself), the following competencies are key:

Communication competencies include knowledge of the necessary languages, ways of interacting with surrounding and distant people and events, skills of working in a group, and mastery of various social roles in a team.

Information competencies. With the help of real objects and information technologies, the ability to independently search, analyze and select the necessary information, organize, transform, save and transmit it is formed.

Personal self-improvement competencies are aimed at mastering methods of physical, spiritual and intellectual self-development, emotional self-regulation and self-support.

Social and labor competencies mean possession of knowledge and experience in the field of civil and social activities - fulfilling the role of a citizen, observer, voter, representative; in the social and labor sphere - the rights of a consumer, buyer, client, manufacturer, in the field of family relations and responsibilities, in matters economics and law, in the field of professional self-determination.

Educational subjects of the natural science cycle examine the properties, connections and interactions of biological, geographical, chemical, physical and technological objects. Moreover, the environment includes both natural and economic, social and cultural components. Integration of subjects within the subject cycle forms in students a complex perception of nature as an integral system with its own cause-and-effect relationships. At the same time, students gain an understanding of the positive and negative impacts of human activity on the natural environment, become aware of local and global environmental problems, and learn to value sustainable and responsible lifestyles, incl. rational and careful use of natural resources, forming their own healthy lifestyle.

CONCLUSION

Thus, the competency-based approach most accurately reflects the essence of processes in the field of education, and a modern teacher should be aimed at mastering technologies for developing students' competencies and mastering the knowledge necessary to implement the competency-based approach.

REFERENCES

1. Features of the formation of functional literacy of students Altynsarina, 2013.
2. Smirnova N.Z., Berezhnaya O.V. Competence-based approach in biological education // Krasnoyarsk, 2012.
3. Zimnyaya I.A. Competence-based approach: what is its place in the system of approaches to educational problems // Higher education today. 2016.
4. Исагалиев, М., Юлдашев, Г., Обидов, М., & Исагалиева, С. (2021). КОЭФФИЦИЕНТ БИОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ПОГЛОЩЕНИЯ МАКРО-И БИОМИКРОЭЛЕМЕНТОВ. In *Аграрная наука-сельскому хозяйству* (pp. 319-321).
5. Isag'aliyeva, S. M. (2023). МАКТАБ О 'QUVCHILARINING BIOLOGIYA DARSLARIDA FUNKSIONAL SAVODXONLIGINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(3), 1225-1229.

6. Исагалиева, С. (2023). BIOLOGIYA O 'QITISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA INTERFAOL USULLARNI QO 'LLASH. *Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences.*, 3(6), 308-312.
7. Закирова, С. Х., Акбаров, Р. Ф., & Исагалиева, С. М. (2020). Водно-физические свойства слабодэфлированных почв в Фергане. In *НАУКА СЕГОДНЯ: ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ И ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ* (pp. 4-5).
8. Isag'aliyeva, S. M. (2022). Baliqlar sinfi mavzusini o 'qitishda qo 'llaniladigan grafik organayzerlar. *Ijodkor o 'qituvchi jurnali*, 23, 422-426.
9. Isag'aliyeva, S. M. (2022). Ta'lim tizimi samaradorligini oshirishning zamonaviy yo 'llari. *Ijodkor o 'qituvchi jurnali*, 23, 427-431.
10. Isagaliyeva, S. (2022, October). Functional literacy as a factor of formation of practical competences. In *I International Scientific and Practical Conference «Challenges and problems of modern science.*